

A CONCEPTUAL REVIEW OF IMTILĀ (REPLETION) IN CONTEXT WITH HYPERTENSION

Mursaleen Naseer¹, Naved Ahmad*², Tabassum Latafat³, Jamal Azmat⁴

^{1,4}Assistant Professor, Department of Moalajat, Ajmal Khan Tibbiya College, Faculty of Unani Medicine, AMU, Aligarh, India.

²MD Scholar, Department of Moalajat, Ajmal Khan Tibbiya College, Faculty of Unani Medicine, AMU, Aligarh, India.

³Professor, Department of Moalajat, Ajmal Khan Tibbiya College, Faculty of Unani Medicine, AMU, Aligarh, India.

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*Corresponding Author

Naved Ahmad

MD Scholar, Department of Moalajat, Ajmal Khan Tibbiya College, Faculty of Unani Medicine, AMU, Aligarh, India.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Hypertension is a major global health problem associated with significant cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. While modern medicine defines it based on elevated arterial pressure, the Unani system describes a comparable condition under *Imtilā* (vascular repletion), reflecting disturbances in the humoral balance and vascular dynamics.

Objective: To critically analyze the Unani concept of hypertension, including its etiopathogenesis, clinical features, and management, and to correlate these principles with contemporary medical understanding. **Methods:** Key concepts such as *Imtilā*, *Mizāj* (temperament), *Akhlāṭ* (humors), and *Quwā* (faculties) were systematically examined and comparatively analyzed with modern pathophysiological mechanisms. **Results:** Unani medicine classifies hypertension into *Imtilā-bi-Hasb-al Awwiyya* (quantitative repletion) and

Imtilā-bi-Hasb-al Quwa (qualitative repletion), corresponding to increased blood volume and altered humoral quality. These mechanisms contribute to vascular tension, arterial stiffness (*Salābat-al-Sharāyīn*), and increased peripheral resistance, closely aligning with modern concepts such as hypervolemia and arteriosclerosis. Lifestyle factors, including an improper

diet, physical inactivity, psychological stress, and disturbed sleep, have consistently been identified as major contributors. Therapeutic approaches emphasize *Usool-e-Ilaj*, including the correction of causative factors, restoration of humoral equilibrium, and evacuation of morbid matter through dietotherapy, regimenal interventions, and pharmacotherapy.

Conclusion: The Unani framework provides a holistic and preventive approach to hypertension, emphasizing lifestyle regulation and individualized care. Its conceptual parallels with modern medicine support its relevance in integrative healthcare; however, further evidence-based clinical studies are required to validate its efficacy.

KEYWORDS: Hypertension, *Imtilā*, Etiopathogenesis, *Mizāj*, *Akhlāt*, *Salābat-al-Sharāyīn*.

INTRODUCTION

Hypertension is a major contributor to global morbidity and mortality and a significant risk factor for cardiovascular, cerebrovascular, and renal diseases, including congestive heart failure, ischemic and hemorrhagic stroke, chronic renal failure, and peripheral arterial disease. It affects more than one billion individuals worldwide and accounts for a substantial proportion of all preventable deaths. According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2023), approximately 1.28 billion adults aged 30-79 years are living with hypertension, with a considerable burden in low- and middle-income countries.^[1,2]

Clinically, hypertension is defined as a sustained elevation of arterial blood pressure and is broadly classified as primary (essential) or secondary hypertension. Primary hypertension constitutes the majority of cases and is associated with multiple risk factors, including genetic predisposition, dietary patterns, obesity, physical inactivity, and psychosocial stress.^[3]

The Unani system of medicine provides a distinct conceptual framework for understanding these conditions. Classical texts do not recognize hypertension as an independent disease entity; instead, a comparable clinical state is described under *Imtilā* (vascular repletion), particularly *Imtilā-bi-Hasb-al Awwiyya*, indicating increased vascular tension due to humoral imbalance.^[8]

This concept is closely related to disturbances in *Akhlāt* (humors), *Mizāj* (temperament), and *Quwā* (faculties), as elaborated by scholars such as Ibn Sina, Razi, and al-Majusi.^[20] These principles show notable parallels with modern pathophysiological mechanisms, including increased blood volume, vascular resistance, and arterial stiffness.

Given the growing interest in integrative medicine, it is important to critically evaluate traditional concepts in the context of contemporary biomedical knowledge. Therefore, this review aims to analyze the Unani concept of hypertension, focusing on its etiopathogenesis, clinical features, and management, and to correlate these principles with the modern scientific understanding.

Unani Concept of Hypertension

The concept of blood pressure was recognized by ancient Unani physicians, who described the systolic and diastolic phases as *Zaghta-e-Inqabāzī* (pressure during contraction) and *Zaghta-e-Inbesāzī* (pressure during relaxation), respectively.^[8] In contemporary Unani literature, hypertension is commonly referred to as *Ḍaght al-Dam Qawī*. However, this term is relatively recent and cannot be directly traced in classical Unani texts.

Classical Unani scholars did not define hypertension as a separate disease entity; instead, they described a closely related clinical condition under the concept of *imtilā* (vascular repletion). Classical descriptions of *Imtilā* closely correspond to the clinical manifestations of hypertension. Based on this, modern Unani physicians have correlated hypertension with *Imtilā* and adopted the term *Ḍaght al-Dam Qawī* to represent this condition.^[4]

The fundamental basis of this concept lies in the theory of *Akhlāṭ* (four humors), namely *Dam* (blood), *Balgham* (phlegm), *Safrā* (yellow bile), and *Saudā* (black bile).^[5] According to Unani principles, the maintenance of health depends on the equilibrium of these humors, while disease arises due to disturbances in their quantity (*kamiyat*) or quality (*kaifiyat*). In the case of *Imtilā*, both quantitative excess and qualitative alteration of humors contribute to the development of vascular congestion and increased tension within vessels.^[20]

Imtilā is primarily expressed in two forms: quantitative repletion, where there is an increase in the volume of circulating humors, particularly blood, and qualitative repletion, where the nature and properties of humors are altered due to impaired digestion and metabolism. These disturbances lead to the accumulation of morbid matter within the vascular system, resulting in distension, increased vascular resistance, and persistence of elevated pressure.^[11,18,16]

In Unani medicine, hypertension is understood as a manifestation of an underlying humoral imbalance, rather than an isolated disease entity. The correlation between *Imtilā* and

hypertension provides a conceptual bridge between classical Unani theory and the modern clinical understanding of elevated blood pressure.

Definition of *Imtilā*

Imtilā is a classical Unani concept that literally denotes the “fullness” or “repletion” of the body with fluids. In technical terms, it refers to the accumulation of bodily fluids (*Akhlāt*), either normal (*Khilt-e-Tabai*) or abnormal (*Khilt-e-Ghair-Tabai*), in the vascular system or other tissues of the body.^[8,10,11,12,13,14,15,16]

Historically, Unani physicians described *Imtilā* as a pathological state of congestion in which excessive intake of food and drink, along with sedentary habits and lack of physical activity, led to the retention of waste products (*Fudūl*) in the body. According to scholars such as Razi, Ibn Sina, and Ali Ibn Abbas Majusi, this accumulation results in an increase in blood volume, vascular distension, and tension within the vessel walls.^[21,22]

The pathophysiological consequences of *Imtilā* include increased vascular pressure and impaired circulation due to the buildup of humoral substances. Additionally, weakness in the vascular structures, particularly the arterial walls, is considered an important contributing factor that facilitates the stagnation and accumulation of abnormal humors at specific sites.

Thus, *Imtilā* represents a state of quantitative or qualitative humoral imbalance leading to vascular congestion and increased tension, which in modern interpretation closely parallels the hemodynamic alterations observed in hypertension.

Unani Classification of *Imtilā*

In the Unani system, the clinical state corresponding to hypertension is understood under the concept of *Imtilā*, which reflects disturbances in the quantity and quality of humors. It is primarily classified into two forms: *imtilā-bi-Hasb-al Awwiyya* (quantitative repletion) and *imtilā-bi-Hasb al-Quwa* (qualitative repletion).

1. *Imtilā-bi-Hasb-al Awwiyya* (Quantitative Repletion)

This form arises due to an increase in the quantity of humors, particularly blood, within the vascular channels, without an initial qualitative change. Excess volume leads to vascular distension (*Tamaddud*) and increased intravascular tension (*Urūqī Tanāo*).^[4,18,16] The fundamental pathology involves expansion of the vascular bed due to overfilling, which clinically manifests as a full and bounding pulse, facial congestion, heaviness, and a tendency

toward epistaxis. This pattern closely parallels the conditions associated with increased circulatory volumes in contemporary medicine.

2. *Imtilā-bi-Hasb al-Quwa* (Qualitative Repletion)

In contrast, this type is characterized by alterations in the quality of humor rather than its quantity. The formation and circulation of morbid materials (*Fāsid Mawād*) result from impaired functional faculties (*Quwā*), particularly the governing and digestive faculties. These qualitative disturbances exert pathological effects on the vascular system, even in relatively small amounts, leading to systemic manifestations and vascular dysfunction without significant hypervolemia. This form reflects functional and metabolic derangements comparable to those described in modern pathophysiology.^[20]

Classification Based on Predominant Humor (*Akhlāt*)

Beyond mechanistic classification, Unani scholars also describe variations based on the dominance of specific humors and the resulting temperament of the individual.^[17]

1. *Damvī* (Sanguineous)

This pattern is associated with the predominance of *Dam* (blood) and a *Hārr Ratab* (hot and moist) temperament. The principal feature is vascular congestion due to increased blood volume, resulting in signs such as facial flushing, warmth of the body, distended vessels, and full pulse. It is commonly observed in individuals with sedentary habits and excessive nutritional intake and bears a resemblance to volume-dependent hypertension.^[17]

2. *Saudāvī* (Melancholic)

This type is associated with the predominance of *Saudā* (black bile) and a *Bārid Yābis* (cold and dry) temperament. The primary pathological feature is dryness and rigidity of the blood vessels (*Yubūsat-al-Urūq* and *Salābat-al-Sharāyīn*), leading to increased vascular resistance. Clinically, this corresponds to arterial stiffness and reduced vascular compliance, similar to chronic or long-standing hypertension.^[17]

Pathophysiology

In the Unani system of medicine, the pathophysiology of hypertension is primarily explained through the concept of *Imtilā* (vascular repletion), which refers to the accumulation of morbid matter (*Mawād-e-Fāsida*) within the vascular system.^[20] This state develops due to various predisposing factors, including excessive dietary intake, alcohol consumption, a sedentary

lifestyle, and other unhealthy habits, leading to increased intravascular volume and vascular tension.

Two principal mechanisms are described in Unani literature.^[30] The first is *Imtilā-bi-Hasb-al Awwiyya* (quantitative repletion), characterized by an increase in the volume of circulating humors, particularly blood (*dam*).^[11,18,16] This results in vascular distension (*Tamaddud*) and increased tension within vessel walls (*Urūqī Tanāo*), corresponding to volume-mediated elevation of blood pressure.^[10]

The second mechanism is *Imtilā-bi-Hasb al-Quwa* (qualitative repletion), in which the primary disturbance lies in altered humoral quality (*Kaifiyat*) and impairment of functional faculties (*Quwā*).^[20] Even small amounts of morbid material can disrupt vascular function due to derangement of *Quwwat-e-Tabia*, *Quwwat-e-Nafsaniya*, and *Quwwat-e-Mudabbira Badan*, resulting in increased vascular resistance without significant hypervolemia.^[20]

Structural vascular changes play a central role in the maintenance of hypertension. Classical descriptions, such as *Yaboosat al-Urūq* (vascular dryness) and *Salābat-al-Sharāyīn* (arterial stiffness), reflect reduced vascular elasticity and impaired vasomotor function. These changes, attributed to *Saudā Muḥarraḡ* (morbid black bile), lead to luminal narrowing and a persistent elevation in vascular resistance.

From a humoral perspective, hypertension is associated with specific temperament patterns. The *Damvī* (sanguineous) temperament corresponds to increased blood volume and quantitative repletion, whereas the *Saudāvī* (melancholic) temperament is characterized by excessive dryness, leading to vascular stiffness and increased peripheral resistance. Dietary factors, particularly excessive intake of cold and dry foods, further promote *Saudā* formation, aggravating vascular rigidity.

Dysfunction of these faculties further contributes to disease progression. The predominance of *Quwwat-e-Māsika* (retentive faculty) and weakness of *Quwwat-e-Dāfi‘a* (expulsive faculty) result in the retention of *Fuḍūl* (waste materials), while impairment of *Quwwat-e-Ghāziya* (digestive faculty) leads to the formation of abnormal humors, which circulate within vessels and increase vascular resistance.

Additionally, the predominance of *Ḥarārat* (heat) and *Yaboosat* (dryness) produces a *Ḥārr Yābis Mizāj* (hot-dry temperament), favoring vascular rigidity and reduced vascular

compliance. The accumulation of *Rūḥ* (pneuma) further contributes to vascular distension and tension.

Thus, the Unani understanding of hypertension involves the interplay of increased blood volume, qualitative humoral alterations, vascular stiffness, and dysfunction of regulatory faculties, ultimately leading to sustained vascular tension and elevated blood pressure, closely corresponding to the modern concepts of hypervolemia, increased peripheral resistance, and arterial stiffness.

Flowchart representation of Sue Mizaj Yabis leading to Imtila

Source: Ali et al. 2025.

Asbāb wa Mahiyat-ul-Marz of Hypertension

In Unani medicine, hypertension (*Ḍaght al-Dam Qawī*) is interpreted through *Imtilā* (vascular repletion) and explained within the framework of *Asbāb-e-Marz*, comprising *Asbāb-e-Souriya* (formal), *Asbāb-e-Maddia* (material), *Asbāb-e-Fā'iliyya* (efficient), and predisposing causes.^[8,19]

1. *Asbāb-e-Souriya* (Formal Causes)

The formal basis of hypertension involves derangement of *Mizāj* (temperament), *Quwā* (faculties), and *Tarkīb* (structure). A predominance of *Mizāj-e-Yābis* (dry temperament), particularly with advancing age, leads to *Yaboosat-e-Urūq* (vascular dryness), resulting in narrowing of vessels, increased resistance, and hard pulse. Classical scholars such as Razi

and Ibn Rushd emphasized that dryness reduces vascular caliber and elevates vascular tension.^[19]

Disturbance of faculties also contributes significantly to the overall stress. Dominance of *Quwwat-e-Māsika* (retentive faculty) and weakness of *Quwwat-e-Dāfi'a* (expulsive faculty) lead to retention of *Fuḍūl* (waste materials), while impairment of *Quwwat-e-Ghāziya* (digestive faculty) results in formation of abnormal humors that circulate within vessels and promote *Imtilā*.^[19]

Structural alterations, particularly *Salābat-al-Sharāyīn* (arterial stiffness), further sustain the elevated vascular tension. Reduced arterial elasticity decreases compliance and maintains increased resistance even without significant volume changes.^[19]

2. *Asbāb-e-Maddia* (Material Causes)

Material causes include *Arkān* (elements), *Arwāḥ* (pneuma), *Akhlāṭ* (humors), and *Azā* (organs). Predominance of *Ḥarārat* (heat) and *Yaboosat* (dryness) produces a *Ḥārr Yābis Mizāj* (hot-dry temperament), often associated with the dominance of *Rukn-e-Nār* (fire element), which predisposes to vascular rigidity and increased pressure.^[19]

Accumulation of *Rūḥ* (pneuma) contributes to vascular distension (*Tamaddud*) and tension (*Tanāo*), particularly when circulatory volume exceeds vascular capacity.^[19]

Among humoral factors, excess *Dam* (blood) plays a key role, leading to *Imtilā-bi-Hasb al-Aw'iyya* (quantitative repletion), whereas qualitative alterations in humors further impair vascular function. Lifestyle factors such as improper diet, physical inactivity, and accumulation of *Fuḍūl* aggravate these changes.^[19]

Hypertension primarily involves the *Qalb* (heart) and *Sharāyīn* (blood vessels), with regulatory influence from the *Dimāgh* (brain) and *Kulliya* (kidneys), which maintain vascular tone and fluid balance.^[19]

3. *Asbāb-e-Fā'iliyya* (Efficient Causes)

Efficient causes include disturbances in *Asbāb-e-Sitta Zarooriya* (six essential factors of life) and *Asbāb-e-Ghair Zarooriya* (non-essential factors), which act as initiating and modifying influences.^[11,16,23,24]

Imbalances in essential factors such as air, diet, physical activity, mental state, sleep, and elimination contribute significantly to disease development. Excessive intake of salt and fat, sedentary habits, psychological stress, disturbed sleep, and impaired elimination promote the accumulation of morbid matter and the progression of *Imtilā*.^[16,25,26]

Non-essential factors, including age, sex, lifestyle habits (smoking and alcohol consumption), environmental influences, and obesity, further modify disease progression. Aging is particularly associated with increased dryness and vascular stiffness.^[19]

4. *Asbāb-e-Tamāmiyya* (Predisposing Causes)

Predisposing factors facilitate the onset and persistence of hypertension by altering the physiological balance. These include the dominance of *Quwwat-e-Māsika*, weakness of *Quwwat-e-Dāfi‘a*, reduced vascular elasticity, increased cardiac force, and enhanced neural activity. These mechanisms collectively sustain vascular tension and predispose individuals to chronic diseases.

ETIOPATHOGENESIS OF HYPERTENSION^[20]***Mahiyat-ul-Marz (Pathogenesis)***

The pathogenesis of hypertension in Unani medicine centers on the development of *Imtilā*, which arises from the interaction of various etiological factors and occurs in two forms: *Imtilā-bi-Hasb-al Awwiyya* (quantitative) and *Imtilā-bi-Hasb al-Quwa* (qualitative). In the former, increased blood volume produces vascular distension (*Tamaddud*) and tension (*Urūqī Tanāo*). In the latter, qualitative derangement of humors leads to the formation of *Fāsīd Mawād*, impairing vascular function even without a significant increase in volume. Concomitantly, *Yaboosat-e-Mizāj* (dry temperament) induces narrowing and rigidity of vessels, resulting in *Salābat al-Sharayīn* (arterial stiffness), and increased peripheral resistance. Derangement of *Quwā* further contributes to the retention of *Fuḍūl* (waste materials), which circulate within vessels and aggravate vascular dysfunction. Thus, hypertension in the Unani framework represents a multifactorial process involving humoral imbalance, altered temperament, impaired faculties, and structural vascular changes, ultimately leading to a sustained elevation in blood pressure.

Correlation of clinical features of Hypertension and *Imtila*^[20]

Symptoms	Hypertension	<i>Imtila-ba-hasbil aw'iyya</i> Repletion concerning vessels	<i>Imtila-ba-hasbil quwa</i> Repletion with vitality
Headache	+	+	-
Palpitation	+	+	-
Dizziness	+	+	+
Breathlessness	+	+	-
Fatigability	+	+	+
Epistaxis	+	+	-
Blurring of vision	+	+	-
Redness of face	+	+	+
Confusion	+	+	+
Chest pain	+	-	+
Diaphoresis	+	-	+
Fullness of pulse	+	+	-
Loss of libido	+	-	+
Weakness	-	-	+
Hot touch of skin	-	+	-
Loss of appetite	-	+	+
Yawning	-	+	-
Constrained speech	-	+	-
Nightmares	-	-	+

The clinical presentation of hypertension is more similar to *Imtilā-bi-Hasb-al Awwiyya* than to *Imtilā-bi-Hasb al-Quwa*, particularly in terms of vascular fullness and volume-related manifestations.

Complications of *Imtilā*

In severe *Imtilā*, which may lead to *Nuzūf* (hemorrhage), *Sakta* (apoplexy), and sudden death, immediate *Faşd* (venesection) is advised to relieve vascular overfilling.^[10,13,18,31]

Unani scholars also described clinical states resembling the consequences of sustained vascular tension, including *Waja-al-Qalb* (angina pectoris), *Ruāf* (epistaxis), cardiac dilatation, cardiac hypertrophy, *Falij* (paralysis), and *Nuzūf-e-Maqad* (rectal bleeding).^[22,31,32]

Classical explanations further note that *Fasād al-Dam* (derangement of blood) may manifest as external bleeding through natural passages when intravascular strain becomes excessive.^[20]

Unani Management of Hypertension

Hypertension is largely a lifestyle-related disorder, and Avicenna emphasized lifestyle modification (*Husn-e-Tadbeer*) as an effective approach for its prevention and management.

Low sodium intake

Excess sodium intake (>2 g/day, approximately 5 g of salt) along with inadequate potassium intake (<3.5 g/day) contributes to hypertension and increases the risk of cardiovascular, cerebrovascular, and renal disease. Dietary sodium is mainly derived from salt and other condiments. Reducing salt intake to less than 5 g/day significantly lowers blood pressure.^[6]

Body weight management

Maintaining an optimal body weight is essential, as being overweight and obese is strongly associated with hypertension. Reduction in body Weight loss results in significant blood pressure reduction, independent of other interventions.^[7]

Reduction of smoking and alcohol consumption

Tobacco use causes acute increases in blood pressure and heart rate; therefore, tobacco cessation is strongly advised. Alcohol intake should be limited, as excessive consumption contributes to hypertension. Recommended limits are up to one drink per day for women and two drinks per day for men.^[6]

Regular physical activity

Moderate-intensity exercise reduces blood pressure by approximately 5-7 mmHg and contributes to long-term control of hypertension.^[31]

In Unani medicine, hypertension is managed as a disorder of *Imtilā* and a humoral imbalance. Treatment focuses on the removal of causative factors (*izala-e-sabab*), correction of temperament (*tadeel-e-mizāj*), evacuation of morbid matter (*tanqiya-e-mawād-e-fāsida*), and strengthening of vital organs. These principles are implemented through *Usool-e-Ilaj*, which integrates preventive measures, dietotherapy, regimen therapy, and pharmacotherapy.^[27]

1. *Tahaffuzi Tadabeer* (Preventive Measures)

Prevention is primarily achieved through the regulation of *Asbāb-e-Sitta Zarooriya* (six essential factors of life), which play a key role in maintaining physiological balance and in preventing vascular dysfunction.

Dietary regulation (*Makool-wa-Mashroob*) emphasizes moderation and avoidance of excessive salt, fat, and heavy meal intake. Regular physical activity (*Harkat-wa-Sukoon-e-Badani*) supports circulation, whereas psychological balance (*Harkat wa Sukoon-e-Nafsanī*) helps reduce stress-related effects on blood pressure.

Adequate sleep (*Naum-wa-Yaqza*) and proper elimination (*Istifrāgh*) are essential to prevent morbid matter accumulation. Environmental factors (*Hawa-e-Muheet*), including clean air and proper ventilation, contribute to overall health. Avoidance of harmful habits such as smoking, alcohol consumption, and excessive mental strain is strongly recommended.^[13,27]

2. *Ilaj bil Ghiza* (Dietotherapy)

Dietotherapy is a key component in hypertension management. The principle of *Taqleel-e-Ghiza* (reduction in dietary quantity and richness) helps decrease vascular load and restore humoral balance.^[28]

Dietary regulation includes appropriate quantity, timing, and sequence of food intake, which supports optimal digestion (*Huḍūm Arba*) and prevents the formation of abnormal humors.^[10]

Therapeutic dietary modifications include

- Reduction of caloric and fat intake to prevent obesity and vascular congestion
- Controlled protein intake based on disease severity^[18]

- Increased consumption of fruits, vegetables, and coarse grains for metabolic and vascular benefits^[18]
- Inclusion of potassium- and calcium-rich foods, particularly fruits, vegetables, and low-fat dairy products, due to their antihypertensive effects.^[18]

Specific dietary classifications include

- *Ghiza-e-Lateef* (light, easily digestible diet), which reduces the metabolic burden;
- *Ghiza Mufarrigh* (diuretic foods), such as coriander, cumin, almonds, and carrots, which facilitate the removal of excess fluids;
- *Ghiza Mulattif* (blood-thinning diet), including honey, figs, and pistachios, helps reduce blood viscosity and prevent vascular obstruction.
- Heavy, spicy, highly refined, or difficult-to-digest foods are discouraged, as they promote the formation of viscid humors and increase vascular tension.^[29]

3. *Ilaj bit Tadbeer* (Regimenal Therapy)

Regimen therapy (*Ilaj bit Tadbeer*) is a major non-pharmacological approach aimed at the evacuation of morbid matter and correction of lifestyle disturbances. These interventions improve physiological functions and vascular dynamics.

Common modalities include

- *Fasd* (venesection): Reduces blood volume, particularly in *Imtilā-e-Damī*
- *Hijāmah bil Sharḥ* (wet cupping): Removes stagnant blood and relieves congestion
- *Ishāl* (purgation): Eliminates morbid humors from deeper tissues
- *Riyāzat* (exercise): Enhances circulation and arterial elasticity
- *Dalk* (massage): Improves peripheral circulation and reduces stress
- *Ḥammām* (steam bath): Promotes perspiration and detoxification
- *Nuṭūl* (irrigation): Provides symptomatic relief
- *Taleeq* (leech therapy) and *Tareeq* (diaphoresis): Help in reducing vascular congestion

These measures collectively improve vascular function and support the restoration of physiological balance.

4. *Ilaj bil Dawa* (Pharmacotherapy)

Pharmacotherapy in Unani medicine focuses on the removal of morbid humors, reduction of vascular resistance, and strengthening of vital organs (*Muqawwiyāt*). Treatment is often

sequential, beginning with *Tanqiya-e-Saudā* through *Mundij* (concoctive) and *Mushil* (purgative) therapies, followed by the correction of temperament.

Drugs used for hypertension act through multiple mechanisms, including

- *Latafat* (blood thinning)
- *Tahallul* (resolution of viscid matter)
- *Istifrāgh* (elimination of excess humors)

Major categories include

- *Mufattehat* (vasodilators): e.g., *Terminalia arjuna*, *Allium sativum*
- *Musakkinat* (sedatives): e.g., *Rauwolfia serpentina*, *Convolvulus pluricaulis*
- *Mufarrehat* (exhilarants): e.g., *Santalum album*, *Abresham*
- *Mudirrat* (diuretics): e.g., *Cucumis sativus*, *Tribulus terrestris*
- *Munawwimat* (hypnotics): for calming and improving sleep

Several single drugs and compound formulations have demonstrated antihypertensive, antioxidant, and cardioprotective effects in both experimental and clinical studies.

CONCLUSION

Hypertension remains a major global health challenge with significant implications for cardiovascular morbidity and mortality, and requires a comprehensive approach beyond conventional biomedical models.

The Unani system conceptualizes hypertension within the framework of *Imtilā* (vascular repletion), representing a state of humoral imbalance with associated alterations in temperament and vascular function. Its classification into quantitative and qualitative forms parallels modern concepts such as hypervolemia, increased peripheral resistance, and arterial stiffness.

Unani medicine adopts a holistic and individualized approach, integrating dietotherapy, regimen, pharmacotherapy, and lifestyle modifications. These strategies aim to correct underlying imbalances and prevent disease progression, rather than focusing solely on symptom control.

The conceptual alignment between Unani principles and modern pathophysiology underscores its potential relevance in integrative health care. However, further well-designed

experimental and clinical studies are required to validate these approaches and establish their roles in evidence-based practice.

REFERENCES

1. Kasper D, Fauci A, Hauser S, Longo D, Jameson J, Loscalzo J. Harrison's Principles of Internal Medicine, Vol 2. New York, NY, USA:McGraw-Hill, 2015.
2. Munjal YP, Sharma SK, Agarwal AK, Gupta P, Kamath SA, Singhal RK, Sunder S, Varma S. API Textbook of Medicine, 9th ed. Mumbai: The Association of Physicians, 2012; 1: 885–887.
3. World Health Organization (WHO). International Society of Hypertension (ISH) Statement on Management of Hypertension. *Journal of Hypertension*, 2003; 21: 1983-1992. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00004872-200311000-00002>
4. Iqbal N, Ali SR SR, Ansari AA, Khan KZ, Khan BD, Ahmad N. Concept of hypertension (Ḍaght al-Dam Qawī) in the Unani system of medicine. *Int Pharm Sci*. 2013 Apr; 3: 2.
5. Raeesuddeen SM. Evaluation of Efficacy of Hijamat Bil Shurt on Ḍaght al-Dam Qawī Ibtida. Bangalore: Dissertation submitted to the RGUHS of Health Sciences, 2010; 5-49.
6. Samad A, Aijaz A. Etiopathogenesis of hypertension in Unani Medicine. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 2022; 9: 9(3).
7. Sina I. *Kitab Al-Shifa (Arabic Edition)*. Beirut: Academic Institution for Studies and Publishing, 1988.
8. Shah H Mazhar. The general principles of Avicenna's Canon of Medicine. *Idara Kitab-ul-Shifa*, New Delhi, 2007; 36, 227-228, 300-301, 392.
9. Saleem S, Ansari AH, Ansari A. Understanding hypertension according to the Unani perspective: an analytical review. *Eur J Pharm Med Res.*, 2020; 7(3): 463–470.
10. Zakaria. *Kitabu-ul-Mansoori (Urdu Translation)* CCRUM, New Delhi, 1991; 74-75, 153-154, 160- 161, 319-320, 342,455.
11. Gruner, Oskar Cameron. *A treatise on The Canon of Medicine of Avicenna*. AMS press, New York, 1973; 276-277,311,177.
12. Razi-Z, *Kitabul Hawi*. Urdu Translation by CCRUM, New Delhi, 1997; I: 54,239-242, 17: 31.
13. Razi A B M B. *Kitabul Murshid*. Urdu translation by M Raziul Islam Nadvi. Urdu Taraqqi Bureau, New Delhi., 2000; 43-46,52-57, 54-56,61-62.
14. Majoosi Ali Ibn-e-Abbas. *Kamil-us-Sana*. Urdu Translation by Ghulam Husain Kantoori. *Idara Kitab-ul-Shifa*, New Delhi, 2010; 176-177, 237-238,372-377, 548.

15. Sina. AL Qanoon Fil Tib, (Urdu translated by Kantoori GH). Vol. I,4 New Delhi: Idara Kitabul Shifa, 2010; 124,145-146,216,755,765,1445.
16. Ibn-e-Sina. Canon of Medicine. English translation of a critical Arabic text. Department of Islamic Studies, Jamia Hamdard, New Delhi, India, 1993; 198-199,264-265.
17. Iqbal MN, Ali SR, Ansari AA, Khan KZ, Khan BD, Ahmad N. Concept of Hypertension (Daght al Dam Qawī) in the Unani System of Medicine. *Int Pharm Sci.*, 2013; 3(2).
18. Ibn-e-Sina. Kulliyat-e-qanoon. Urdu translation by Kabeeruddin, Vol.1, 2. Idara Kitab-ul-Shifa, 2015; 192, 238-239. 35-37, 311-312.
19. Samad A, Aijaz A. Etiopathogenesis of hypertension in Unani medicine. *J Emerg Technol Innov Res.*, 2022; 9(3): 237–242.
20. Goldman L, Schafer I. A. Cecil medicine., 26th edition.Saunders Elsevier, 2020; 443.
21. Azmi W.A. Moalejat. Amraz Nizam Asab wa Dauran-e-khoon. Qaumi council barafarogh urdu zaban, 2008; 1: 322-327.
22. Md. Nafis Iqbal, et al. Concept of Hypertension (Daght al-Dam Qawī) in Unani system of Medicine. *Internationale Pharmaceutica Scientia*, 2013; 3(2): 1-5.
23. Ahmed, Hakim Syed Ishtiyah, Al-Umur Al-Tabiyah, 1st ed., Saini Printers Pahari Dhiraj, Delhi., 1980; 75-77, 99 102, 215-221, 223,233.
24. Ibn-e –Sina: Al Qanoon fil Tibb, Urdu translation by Hkm Ghulam Hasnain Qantoori, Idara -e –KitabusShifa, New Delhi, 2010; 97,109,174, 203-204.
25. Kabiruddin M. Kulliyat-e-Nafisi. Idara kitab- ul -Shifa, New Delhi, 1954; 119,319,473-474,188,189,214,234.
26. John Glynn, Nasira Bhikha-Vallee, Rashid Bhikha. Dietotherapy: Let food be your medicine, 2013.
27. Qarshi HM. Jame-ul-Hikmat. Vol.1,2. Idara Kitab-us-Shifa, New Delhi, 2011; 618-622.
28. Usama Akram and N Quddusi. "Importance of Dietary Therapy (Ilaj Bil Ghiza) in Unani System of Medicine". *Acta Sci Nutr Health*, 2020; 4.2: 01-06.
29. Maseehi AS. Kitabul Miyah.Vol 1. CCRUM, New Delhi, 2008; 200-228.
30. Ahmed S. Clinical evaluation of khameera sandal sada in the management of zaghtuddum qavi ibtidai. Karnataka, Bangalore: Rajiv Gandhi University of Health Sciences, 2007.
31. Jeelani Ghulam. Makhzan-e-hikmat. Vol.1. Faisal publications, Deoband, 2009; 880: 101.419-427.
32. Khan MA. Akseer-e-Azam (Al-Akseer). Urdu translation by Hakeem Kabeeruddin. Idara Kitab-ul- Shifa, New Delhi, 2011; 29, 144-146, 165, 175-176, 349-351.